

Original Research Article

Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of Tobacco Consumption in Relation to Oral Diseases amongst Students, Dentists and Non-Teaching Staff of Baqai Dental College Karachi, Pakistan

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Abstract

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Globally, Tobacco is a major cause of premature death and disease. Objective of the study was to assess the Knowledge, attitude and practice of tobacco consumption in relation to oral diseases amongst students, dentists and non-teaching staff of Baqai Dental College Karachi, Pakistan. A cross-sectional study was conducted from June 2018 to February 2019. A simple random technique was used and this cross-sectional study population divided into 3 groups of Baqai Dental College. The pre-tested questionnaires were distributed by the investigators to the three groups. This comparative study included a total of two hundred and eighty five (285) people. 154 were males and 131 were females. Only 9.5% of the people were not aware of certain tobacco products while 90.5% had knowledge of the product. Knowledge about smoking tobacco in cigarette form was 181(63.5%) while 104(36.5%) do not know much about it. Similarly mostly people indicated that they use smokeless tobacco in least amount. In conclusion, this study found a considerably high prevalence of cigarette smoking among male students. Female students had better knowledge of tobacco harms and expressed greater anti tobacco attitudes compared to males. Significant number 95(33.3%) of people had intention to quit cigarette smoking.

Keywords: Baqai, Knowledge, Oral diseases, Smoking tobacco

INTRODUCTION

Globally, Tobacco is a major cause of premature death and disease. Around 5-6 million people die every year due to tobacco consumption and this figure is expected to rise 8 to million a year by 2030 (Tubachi et al., 2018). Tobacco consumption has risen great concern regarding public health as tobacco is the biggest cause of morbidity and mortality in the third world (Murray and Lopez, 1997).

Studies are suggesting that same trend will continue till 2020, and prediction done by Murray 30 years ago is still proving to be true that is tobacco kills half of its user's worldwide.

Locally, Pakistan is the top most consumer of tobacco in the South Asian Region (National Institute of Population Survey, 2015). Pakistan Demographic Health

Survey states 46 % men and 5.7% women smoke tobacco and it is most common among farmers and the young population. In a Statistical Bulletin published by State Bank, it was reported that Rs 250 billion has been spent on 64 billion cigarettes smoked in the year 2014. Thus tobacco consumption is not only causing morbidity and mortality; it is also a great burden on the economy of Pakistan (Khan et al., 2018).

Tobacco is consumed in two ways –smoking and oral smokeless tobacco. Smoking tobacco can be in the form of cigarette, bidi, pipe, e-cigarettes and cigars. It has been proven to increase the risk of developing respiratory and cardiovascular disease, it can also contribute towards the formation of cancer in oral cavity, larynx, esophagus, pancreas and bladder (Kumar et al., 2018). Not only the smoker but the passive smokers or second hand smokers are also exposed to its hazards (National Center for Chronic Disease Prevention and Health Promotion, U.S, 2014). In pregnant women it can lead to teratogenic (developmental) effects, congenital anomalies and low birth weight (Abou-Faddan and Ahmed, 2012).

Use of smokeless tobacco is also rising in Pakistan and other South East Asian countries. It has been proven to be one of the causative agents of oral and pancreatic cancer, periodontal and cardiovascular diseases. Oral tobacco comes in a variety of forms and up to 30 different products with smokeless tobacco are commercially available in the market. These products include Tambaku, Pan, Gutka, and Zarda (Nair et al., 2004).

The present study is first of its kind that is being conducted at Baqai Dental College, Karachi; aimed towards determining the Knowledge, Attitude and Practice of tobacco consumption in relation to oral diseases amongst students, house officers, faculty members and non-teaching staff members of the institute.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A cross-sectional study was conducted from June 2018 to February 2019. A simple random technique was used. and population was divided into 3 group of Baqai Dental College. The pre-tested questionnaires were distributed by the investigators during the class lecture. No student refused to return the questionnaire.

The questionnaire consisted of personal questions like; name, gender, occupation, year of study, complexion, smoking habits (cigarette, pipe, cigar, electronic cigarette etc.) smokeless (pan, gutkha, mawa, naswar etc.) frequency and quantity of smoking, attitude and knowledge about diseases developed due to smoking or smokeless tobacco. group 1 included of all dental students from 1st year to final year, group 2 include all dentists of dental college and group 3 include all non – teaching staff members were selected. All the available

students were requested to participate in the study and consent was taken from teachers/ and respected Out Patients Department (OPDs) in charges of all the participants.

A total of 285 persons aged between 18 to 50 years were randomly selected. A self-administered questionnaire was designed comprised of 16 questions about Knowledge, attitude and practice of tobacco consumption in relation to oral diseases among the students, dentists and non – teaching staff members of Baqai Dental College Karachi were filled by the investigator according to the verbal response given by the participants.

The sample size was calculated by taking 21% proportion and computed using SPSS version 22 at 95% confidence interval and p value is taken 0.05%.

Students, dentists and non- teaching staff members of Baqai Dental College were included in this study population not a part of Baqai Dental College was excluded from study

Descriptive statistics were obtained and mean, standard deviation, frequency and percentages were calculated. Chi- square test was done to assess the association of gender with tobacco consumption.

RESULTS

This comparative study included two hundred and eighty five people (285) which included dental students, dental faculty and non teaching staff of Baqai Dental College Karachi.154 were males and 131 were females.

Only 9.5% people were not aware of certain tobacco products while 90.5% were known to these products. Knowledge about smoking tobacco in cigarette form was 181(63.5%) while 104(36.5%) do not much about it. Similarly mostly people indicated that they use smokeless tobacco in least amount.

Only 97.5% population agreed that tobacco is injurious to oral health and can cause oral cancer while 2.5% were not even aware of this.99 (34.7%) mentioned association between leukoplakia and tobacco consumption and 80 (28.1%) mentioned association between erythroplakia and tobacco while 253(88.8%) people significantly mentioned association between oral cancer and tobacco.

Only 120(42.1%) people observed white and red patches on the inner lining of oral cavity since the use of tobacco products.

There were certain complications among (39.3%) of people and (60.7%) had no complications in this regard. (Figure 1 - 4)

Only 50(17.5%) people indicated that they use these products for addiction purpose and younger students were consuming only for fun purpose while faculty were taking tobacco for anxiety relieving. Meanwhile, about 95(33.3%) people mentioned that they had tried to quit this habit while 190(66.7%) didn't tried to quit.

Figure 1. Percentage of tobacco and non tobacco users.

Figure 2. Showing more respondents consume smoking tobacco as compared to smokeless tobacco

Figure 3. Frequency of Smoking Tobacco Users (n= 285). This chart (3) is showing the ratio of consuming cigarette is greater than other smoking products.

Figure 4. Chart showing the frequency of the Smokeless Tobacco Users (n=285)

DISCUSSION

This study is an attempt to comprehensively assess the knowledge, attitude and practice of tobacco consumption in relation to oral diseases amongst students, dentists and non-teaching staff of Baqai Dental College Karachi,

Pakistan. Majority of the study respondents 97.5% were aware that tobacco leads to oral diseases such as erythroplakia and leukoplakia. The prevalence data on tobacco use among the youth is important both to assess tobacco as a risk factor and to establish control measures for prevention of oral diseases.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study found a considerably high prevalence of cigarette smoking among male students. Female students had better knowledge of tobacco harms and expressed greater anti tobacco attitudes compared to males. Significant number 95(33.3%) of people had intention to quit cigarette smoking. Smoking and smokeless tobacco control among South Asians not only presents a national but a global problem. Information on cigarette smoking and to bring positive behavioral changes through awareness programs is essential to improve the focus of prevention and control measures and thereby succeed in the struggle against tobacco use.

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